

A Pseudo-Seleukid Imitative Owl.

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A newly identified imitative Athenian tetradrachm bearing an anchor symbol sheds light on the development of imitative coinage in the easternmost region of the Seleukid empire during the first half of the 3rd century BC. Analysis of the coin suggests that it was struck in the period 300-250 BC in a part of the eastern Seleukid realm that was not served by an official Seleukid mint. It supports the interpretation that imitative Athenian coinage was struck in parts of this region well into the 3rd century BC.

Imitative Athenian tetradrachms and smaller denominations were struck in various locations throughout the eastern Mediterranean, particularly Egypt and the Levant, from the middle of the 5th century BC.² With the Macedonian conquest, this practice ceased in Egypt and the Levant, the Athenian owl as a currency of regional trade displaced by the mintage of Alexander the Great's imperial coinage. However, the Athenian owl maintained its status as a major currency in mainland Greece for the next century,³ while in the region east of the Tigris, extending into southwestern Central Asia,⁴ newly exposed to monetization, but underserved by imperial mints, imitative Athenian coinage was struck to fill a developing monetary void.⁵ Recently, an undocumented type of imitative Athenian tetradrachm appeared in commerce,⁶ derived from what is described in the numismatic trade as the Andragoras-Sophytes Group of coins.

Uncertain Eastern Seleukid Satrapy, Imitative Athenian AR Tetradrachm.

17.29 g, 23 mm, 3 h.

Obv.: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Attic helmet.

Rev.: Owl standing r., head facing , anchor and crescent behind, AΘE to r.

Ref.: van Alfen (2011) -; previously unknown with the anchor symbol.

¹ This working paper is an extract from a broader study by the author of the phenomenon of mid-3rd century BC imitative coinage produced in a number of the eastern provinces of the Seleukid realm.

² Fisher-Bossert (2008); van Alfen (2011).

³ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990).

⁴ For the purposes of this discussion I use the UNESCO definition of southwestern Central Asia which includes the north-eastern Iran and those states to the north and east i.e. including ancient Parthia, Margiana, Sogdiana and Baktria.

⁵ Van Alfen (2011); Taylor (2019(a)).

⁶ Roma Numismatics E-Sale 73 (23 Jul. 2020), lot 556; the anchor symbol was incorrectly described as an olive spring (*sic*) in the auctioneer's description of the coin.

On this tetradrachm, the detail of the floral ornamentation on Athena's helmet suggests that it was loosely modelled on the late pi-style issues of late 4th century BC Athens.⁷ Although it bears the ethnic AΘE on the reverse, the overall character and style suggests an eastern imitative origin. Even within the diverse stylistic repertoire of imitative owls variously found in Egypt,⁸ Arabia,⁹ Syria,¹⁰ Babylonia/Mesopotamia¹¹ and Parthia,¹² it presents a number of unusual characteristics, most notably the presentation of an anchor in the place of the olive sprig to the left of the crescent behind the owl (Figure 1). This presentation is otherwise unknown. It is a pointer to the probable origin and dating of the coin; aspects that are explored in the following discussion.

Figure 1. Detail: upper left reverse.

In addition to the anchor, another unique departure from the Athenian prototype and the iconography of other imitative Athenian types, is the depiction of Athena with her ear concealed completely by a large lock of hair, defined by four concentric lines, extending from the beneath the helmet bowl on the forehead to intersect and overlap the topmost portion of the helmet neck guard. Although no detail of Athena's ear is visible, a semi-circular earring is depicted below the falling hairline, adjacent to the leading edge of the helmet neck guard. The overall style of the obverse is inelegant. Athena's lips, nose and eye are exaggerated in their delineation. Details are rendered coarsely and the delineation of the base of the helmet neck guard from the trailing locks of Athena's hair is crudely marked by a thick curved line with no attempt at iconographic differentiation of the hair below this line from the surface of helmet above. In the corpus of imitative Athenian coinage, regardless of age or geography, there are no analogues to the detail of the depiction of Athena on this coin.

Due to the unique characteristics of the coin, additional clues to its origin must be sought in the broader context of its entry into numismatic trade. It entered commerce accompanied by the provenance statement "*From the 1960s Andragoras-Sophytes Group, present in Germany in 1975, subsequently exported to the USA.*" This group of more than 400 coins has many of the characteristics of a hoard in commerce. It first came to market in late 2017. Coins of the group continued to appear in the numismatic trade over the next three years.

⁷ Kroll (2011): 232-234 for a summary of the diagnostics of the pi-style coinage.

⁸ Nicolet-Pierre (1979); van Alfen (2011): types III.B.1-3.

⁹ Gitler and Tal (2006); van Alfen (2010); van Alfen (2011): types III.D.1-4.

¹⁰ Van Alfen (2002); Gitler and Tal (2006); van Alfen (2011): types III.C.1-5.

¹¹ Van Alfen (2000); Van Alfen (2011): types III.E.1-2.

¹² Nicolet-Pierre and Amandry (1994); Bopearachchi (1996): Series 1; Bopearachchi (1998): 1-11; Van Alfen (2011): type III.F; Taylor (2019(a)): Series 1 and 2 re-attributed from Uncertain Bactria to Andragoras, Satrap of Parthia.

In one auction the provenance and content of the Andragoras-Sophytes Group was more expansively described:

*"... a highly important group of coins which apparently came to light in the Oxus region in the 1960s, taken to Germany in 1975 when the owners emigrated there, and subsequently exported to the USA. Principally consisting of 'Athenian Series' tetradrachms, didrachms and drachms, also included are some highly important issues bearing the names of Andragoras and Sophytes. Additionally, the group includes (but not presented here) a 4th century drachm of Thebes, two well-worn mid-4th century Tyre owl-type shekels, two official Athens tetradrachms, five regional Athenian imitations, an Amphipolis mint Alexander-type tetradrachm minted circa 316-311 (Price 133), another attributed to the Susa mint, circa 322-320 (Price 3850), and another from the Ekbatana mint, struck under Seleukos circa 311-295 (Price 3899). Lastly (and significantly), the group also contained one elephant-quadruga type tetradrachm of Seleukos (SC 177.5) from the Susa mint, dated 296/5-281 BC. Though the possibility that they were stray finds from the same area cannot be excluded, their condition suggests otherwise and is indicative of having been within a contained and stable environment."*¹³

Contradicting this provenance, in scholarship the same group of coins has been referred to a 2014 find of 600 coins in Afghanistan.¹⁴ As with any hoard identified in commerce, potentially the result of illicit excavation and thus absent any documented context, considerable uncertainty attaches to its true nature, content and location. The surface appearance, texture and the preservation of the newly identified tetradrachm is consistent with the balance of the Andragoras-Sophytes Group sold by the same auction house, so that there is nothing in the available data to challenge the association of the coin with a find that contained a large number of eastern imitative Athenian issues. Imitative owls attributed to the Seleukid satrapy of Parthia under Andragoras¹⁵ (Figures 2 and 4)¹⁶ represented at least fifty percent of the Andragoras-Sophytes Group. In addition, the Andragoras-Sophytes Group also contained a Mesopotamian imitative Athenian tetradrachm of Mazakes,¹⁷ and two Mesopotamian owls bearing the letters ΑΙΓ,¹⁸ accompanied by a number of late 4th century BC pi-style Athenian owls. The association of an anchor symbol bearing imitative Athenian coin with this assemblage suggests that it was minted in east of the Tigris, in the Seleukid era.

Figure 2. Imitative Athenian tetradrachms attributed to Andragoras, satrap of Parthia.

¹³ Roma Numismatics XIV (21 September 2017) Catalogue: 106.

¹⁴ Bordeaux and Bopearachchi (2018): slide 4.

¹⁵ Taylor (2019(a)).

¹⁶ Fig. 2(a) Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 344; Fig. 2(b) Roma Numismatics E-Sale 44, lot 312; Figure 4, both coins from the author's collection.

¹⁷ Van Alfen (2011): type III.E.1.

¹⁸ Van Alfen (2011): type III.E.2.

The tetradrachm weighs 17.29 grams, conforming to the Attic weight standard. A wide distribution of weights is evident in many large samples of imitative Athenian coinage.¹⁹ This appears to be the result of imprecise weight adjustment, nominally to the Attic weight standard. The weight distribution of our largest sample of 3rd century BC eastern imitative Athenian coinage, that of Andragoras (Table 1),²⁰ serves to illustrate the point. Although a little heavier than most imitative Athenian tetradrachms, the coin's weight still falls within the range of weights observed in eastern imitative Athenian coinage from the 3rd century BC.

Table 1. Weights: Andragoras Series 1 and 2 imitative Athenian tetradrachms

	No. of coins	Mean (g)	Median (g)	Mode (g)	Range (g)	Standard Deviation σ (g)
Series 1	75	16.63	16.70	16.70	14.74-17.33	0.49
Series 2	178	16.78	16.84	16.80	15.87-17.24	0.30
Series 1 and 2	253	16.74	16.80	16.80	14.74-17.33	0.37

Turning now to the anchor symbol on the reverse. It is located in the position that is occupied by the olive sprig on the Athenian prototype. Prior to 311 BC the anchor is rarely found on Greek coinage. It is unknown in association with the primary iconography of Athena/Owl. Early depictions of an anchor on Greek coins typically involve thicker flukes, and differing stock and head configurations (Figure 3a-c)²¹ compared to the that of the almost linear slender flukes, stock, and circular head ring of the anchor on the imitative Athenian tetradrachm. After 311 BC, the anchor seal of Seleukos, dating from his time as a *navarch* for Ptolemy I, developed into a dynastic insignia that became a frequent symbol on official Seleukid coinage.²² The anchor on some of the early issues of Seleukos in Babylonia (Figure 3d)²³ that were struck in the last decade of the 4th century BC most closely resembles that found on the imitative Athenian tetradrachm. Yet the presence of the imitative AΘE ethnic accompanying the anchor indicates that this cannot be an official Seleukid issue.

Figure 3. Anchor depictions.

¹⁹ Van Alfen (2000); Van Alfen (2002); Fisher-Bossert (2008); Taylor (2019(a)).

²⁰ Updated from Taylor (2019(a)): fig. 1 and table 5, to include an additional 131 specimens of Series 1 and 2 imitative Athenian tetradrachms from the Andragoras-Sophytes Group.

²¹ Examples being (a) the 6th-5th century BC coinage of Apollonia Pontika, (b) a 5th century BC Samos tetradrachm (HGC 6, 1186) and (c) an uncertain Cyprus mint 5th century BC emission (Asyut pl. XXXII).

²² Taylor (2015) and Taylor (2019(b)).

²³ Tetradrachm of Seleukos I from Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) in Babylonia dating to 308-304 BC; Taylor (2015): Series II. Series II was issued in the name of Alexander and the anchor symbol served to identify Seleukos and the issuing authority.

The placement of what appears to be the Seleukid anchor symbol on the reverse of an imitative Athenian coin is a conundrum. However, it finds a potential explanation and an analogue in the emission of imitative Athenian coinage by Andragoras the satrap of Parthia.²⁴ This coinage was struck for local use by Andragoras using the anonymous²⁵ Athenian owl as a model. It was struck in a comprehensive range of range of denominations. The prominence of the didrachm (Figure 4) in this coinage, accompanied by an array of small denominations, attests to its epichoric character.²⁶ Being an anonymous coinage, motivated by a monetary necessity in a region that was not served by an official Seleukid mint, it could not be perceived as a challenge to Seleukid authority, although the issuing satrap had assumed what was a royal prerogative in issuing coinage without royal assent. This imitative coinage evolved, dispensing with the incuse square reverse of the earliest issues (Series 1) while gradually departing from the Athenian prototype (Series 2), eventually to include various mint control symbols (a grape bunch, a galley prow, and a grape vine branch) on the reverse. A prow symbol mint control displaced the olive sprig and crescent, which were dropped completely from the imitative iconography (Figures 2b and 4b).²⁷

Figure 4. Andragoras Series 2 didrachms illustrating visor hinge development.

Accompanying this progression in mint controls on the larger denominations, the inner end of the decorative visor on Athena's helmet was altered from an open-ended termination (Figure 4a) to that of a closed loop or volute, defining a hinge point above the ear (Figure 4b).²⁸ This feature, a late development, is unknown on any other imitative Athenian coinage, regardless of origin. However, by reference to an identical development on the Athenian prototype²⁹ it can be dated to the middle of the 3rd century BC.³⁰ The absence of this iconographic detail on the anchor bearing imitative owl suggests that it predates the Series 2 coinage of Andragoras.

Similar reasoning suggests that the mintage of the anchor bearing imitative Athenian tetradrachm may have been motivated by need for coinage in a region that was devoid of an official Seleukid mint. An anonymous Athenian prototype was chosen for its politically neutral character and broad regional acceptance. However, the added embellishment of the Seleukid anchor replacing the olive sprig served to indicate beyond doubt fealty to the Seleukid suzerain.

²⁴ Taylor (2019(a)): Series 1 and 2 for a typology, die study and analysis of the coinage.

²⁵ Anonymous in so far as the issuing authority, or mint, were not identified by any mark, or legend, the AΘE ethnic being no more than a component of the overall imitative iconography/epigraphy with no attached meaning in terms of the origin of the coin.

²⁶ Taylor (2019(a)): 64-66.

²⁷ Taylor (2019(a)): 63-64.

²⁸ Taylor (2019(a)): 53-54.

²⁹ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990) Heterogeneous Groups B and C, now attributed by Kroll (2013) as an Athenian civic coinage of the 3rd (Group C) and 2nd (Group B) quarters of the 3rd century BC.

³⁰ Taylor (2020). The closed loop, or volute termination on the decorative visor of Athena's helmet dispels the notion that the Series 2 imitative Athenian coinage dates to the 4th century BC for it was not part of the iconography of the Attic helmet on Athenian coinage at this early date.

Even in the absence of royal assent for the coinage, bearing the Seleukid anchor insignia it would have been readily argued that its mintage was not a challenge to Seleukid royal authority. In this assessment we identify an unofficial, pseudo-Seleukid, imitative Athenian coin, that probably predates the Andragoras Series 2 imitative Athenian issues of the mid 3rd century BC. Together with the other factors previously discussed, this suggests that this imitative Athenian tetradrachm was struck in the period 300-250 BC, somewhere in the east of the Seleukid realm. Possibly, it was a precursor to the substantial imitative Athenian issues of Andragoras, struck in the mid 3rd century BC.

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